

**The Directive Effect of Substituents on the Cyclisation
of Substituted *s*-Diarylthiocarbamides. Part II.
The Effect of the Fluorine Atom on the Thiazole
Cyclisation of *p*-Fluoro-*s*-diphenylthio-
carbamides by Bromine.**

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In view of the attention which has been directed in recent years by Ingold and his collaborators to the effect of fluorine substituents in aromatic substitution (Holmes and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1328; Ingold and Shaw, *ibid.*, 1927, 2918 ; Ingold and Vass, *ibid.*, 1928, 417 ; Ingold and Ingold, *ibid.*, p. 2254), it appeared of interest to include a study of the behaviour of *p*-fluoro-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamides (I) towards bromine in the present investigation (*cf.* Hunter, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 435).

Under the usual conditions of thiazole cyclisation by bromine, the *p*-tolyl-, *p*-bromophenyl-, and 1-*p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamides (I, R=Me, Br and Cl respectively) gave rise to 4'-fluoro-1-anilino-benzthiazoles (II, R=Me, Br and Cl), identical with the bases obtained by condensation of *p*-fluoroaniline with the corresponding 5-substituted 1-chlorobenzthiazoles.

s-*p*-Fluorophenyl-*p*-nitrophenylthiocarbamide (I, R=NO₂), on the other hand, yielded a base isomeric with 4'-fluoro-5-nitro-1-anilino-benzthiazole (II, R=NO₂) obtained from 5-nitrochlorobenzthiazole and *p*-fluoroaniline, which was shown to be 4'-nitro-5-fluoro-1-anilino-

benzthiazole (IV) by its synthesis from 5-fluoro-1-chlorobenzthiazole (III) and *p*-nitroaniline.

The effect of the fluorine atom, therefore, falls into line with that of the other halogens previously studied (Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 458 ; Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2190) ; the inhibitory effect of substituents on benzthiazole formation from thiocarbanilides being in the order : $\text{NO}_2 > \text{F} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{EtO} > \text{Me}$ (cf. Hunter, *Sir P. C. Rây Commemoration Volume*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, p. 79).

EXPERIMENTAL.

s-p-Fluorophenyl-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (I, R=Me).—A solution of *p*-fluorophenylthiocarbimide (Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147) in ethyl acetate (2.3 g. in 8 c.c.) was mixed with a solution of *p*-toluidine (1.8 g.) in the same solvent (8 c.c.) when a pale yellow colour developed and the mixture was concentrated on a steam-bath. On recrystallisation from ethyl acetate (charcoal), the *thiocarbamide* was obtained in glistening plates, m.p. 169°, yield 2.4 g. (Found: S, 12.7. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{FS}$ requires S, 12.3 per cent). In later experiments, the yield was raised to 2.7 g. by substituting benzene for ethyl acetate as the medium of condensation.

4'-Fluoro-1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole (II, R=Me). (i) *Cyclisation of s-p-fluorophenyl-p-tolylthiocarbamide*.—Bromine (1.4 c.c. in 2 c.c. of chloroform) was added to a solution of the fluorophenyl-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (0.8 g.) in chloroform (13 c.c.) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath under reflux, when hydrogen bromide was copiously evolved during the first 10 minutes. Heating was continued for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the resulting solution was concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature when the *hydroperbromide* of the fluoroanilinobenzthiazole crystallised in yellow plates, which were collected on a porous earthenware and dried in vacuum. The bromo-addition compound was added to saturated sulphurous

acid and sulphur dioxide was passed through the mixture until the solid matter was colourless. On basification with ammonia (d 0.880) and recrystallisation from alcohol, 4'-fluoro-1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole was obtained in small crystals which had m. p. 182° alone, and when mixed with the specimen prepared from 1-chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole and *p*-fluoroaniline. (Found: S, 12.2. $C_{14}H_{11}N_2FS$ requires S, 12.3 per cent).

(ii) *Synthesis from 1-chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole and p-fluoroaniline.*—A mixture of 1-chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole (0.9 g.) and *p*-fluoroaniline (0.6 g.) was heated in a wide mouth Pyrex boiling tube over a small naked flame for 2-3 minutes when a vigorous reaction took place. On basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from alcohol, 4'-fluoro-1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole was obtained in small crystals, m.p. 183°.

s-p-Fluorophenyl-p-bromophenylthiocarbamide (I, R=Br), prepared from *p*-fluorophenylthiocarbimide (3 g.) in benzene (10 c.c.) and *p*-bromoaniline (3.5 g.) in the same solvent (10 c.c.), separated from ethyl acetate in glistening plates, m.p. 159-60° (4.7 g.), which on further recrystallisation from benzene finally melted at 164-65°. (Found: S, 9.8. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2BrFS$ requires S, 9.8 per cent).

4'-Fluoro-5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole (II, R=Br). (i) *Cyclisation of s-p-fluorophenyl-p-bromophenylthiocarbamide.*—The fluorophenyl-bromophenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) suspended in chloroform (10 c.c.), was treated with bromine (0.7 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was refluxed for 12 minutes and the *hydroperbromide* was collected on a porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum in the usual way. It formed orange yellow plates, m.p. 165-66°, which were added to sulphurous acid and treated with sulphur dioxide until all solid matter was colourless. On basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from alcohol, 0.45 g. of 4'-fluoro-5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole, m.p. 210° was obtained. On repeated recrystallisation from ethyl acetate, in which the base is very soluble, the melting point was finally raised to 218-19°. A mixture of this with 4'-fluoro-5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole obtained from the condensation of 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole and *p*-fluoroaniline melted at 221-22°. In a similar experiment in which a suspension of the fluorophenylbromophenylthiocarbamide (0.8 g.) in chloroform (13 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1.5 c.c. in 1.5 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the first crop of 4'-fluoro-5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole

obtained by recrystallisation of the base from the reduction of the hydroperbromide had m. p. 216° , and m. p. $221-22^{\circ}$ when mixed with a genuine specimen. The second crop of crystals, however, had m. p. 170° which was further depressed by admixture with 4'-fluoro-5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole and appeared to consist mainly of unchanged fluorophenylbromophenylthiocarbamide. A similar result was also obtained by treating a solution of fluorophenylbromophenylthiocarbamide (0.9 g.) in chloroform (25 c. c.) with bromine (1.6 c. c. in 2.5 c. c. of chloroform).

(ii) *Synthesis from 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole and p-fluoroaniline.*—An intimate mixture of 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole (1.2 g.) and *p*-fluoroaniline (0.5 g.) was heated until a violent reaction took place. On basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from ethyl acetate, 4'-fluoro-5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained in soft glistening plates, m. p. $222-23^{\circ}$. (Found: Br, 24.6; S, 10.1. $C_{13}H_8N_2BrFS$ requires Br, 24.8; S, 9.9 per cent).

s-p-Fluorophenyl-p-chlorophenylthiocarbamide, prepared by condensation of benzene solutions of *p*-fluorophenylthiocarbimide (2.3 g.) and *p*-chloroaniline (1.9 g.), separated from benzene in glistening plates, m. p. $158-59^{\circ}$. (Found: S, 11.9. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2ClFS$ requires S, 11.8 per cent).

4'-Fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole. (i) *Cyclisation of s-p-fluorophenyl-p-chlorophenylthiocarbamide.*—Bromine (1.6 c. c. in 2.5 c. c. of chloroform) was added to the fluorophenylchlorophenylthiocarbamide (0.9 g.) in chloroform (23 c. c.), and the mixture was heated under reflux for 30 minutes and cooled in ice. The bromo-addition compound was dried in vacuum in the usual way, suspended in sulphurous acid and treated with sulphur dioxide until reduction was complete. On basification and recrystallisation from alcohol—ethyl acetate, 4'-fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained which had m. p. 218° , and m. p. 222° when mixed with a specimen of the base obtained by condensation of 1:5-dichlorobenzthiazole with *p*-fluoroaniline. The base obtained from the mother liquors had m. p. 172° which rose to 190° when mixed with genuine 4'-fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole and contained thiocarbamide which had escaped cyclisation. In a similar experiment in which 0.7 g. of the fluorophenylchlorophenylthiocarbamide in chloroform (10 c. c.) was treated with bromine (1.4 c. c. in 2 c. c. of chloroform), 4'-fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was isolated which had m. p. $219-20^{\circ}$ alone, and m. p. $220-22^{\circ}$ when mixed with a specimen obtained

from the dichlorobenzthiazole. In another experiment in which 0.5 g. of the thiocarbamide in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.8 c. c. in 1 c. c. of chloroform) and heating was continued for 43 minutes, the first crop of 4'-fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole obtained on recrystallisation from methyl alcohol had m. p. 218° alone, and m. p. 219-20° when mixed with a genuine specimen. The base obtained from the mother liquors, however, had m. p. 172° which rose to 184° on admixture with 4'-fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole, and contained free thiocarbamide which was detected by alkaline lead solution in the usual way.

(ii) *Synthesis from 1:5-dichlorobenzthiazole and p-fluoroaniline.*—An intimate mixture of 1:5-dichlorobenzthiazole (*vide* Part iii, p. 563) and *p*-fluoroaniline in equimolecular proportions was heated until a violent reaction took place. On basification and recrystallisation from alcohol—ethyl acetate, 4'-fluoro-5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained in soft glistening plates, m. p. 222-23°. (Found: Cl, 12.7; S, 12.0. $C_{13}H_8N_2ClFS$ requires Cl, 12.7; S, 11.9 per cent).

s-p-Nitrophenyl-p-fluorophenylthiocarbamide, prepared by condensation of equimolecular proportions of *p*-nitrophenylthiocarbimide (Dyson and George, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1702) and *p*-fluoroaniline in benzene, separated from absolute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 170-71°. (Found: S, 11.2. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_3FS$ requires S, 11.1 per cent).

4'-Nitro-5-fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole (IV). (i) *Cyclisation of s-p-nitrophenyl-p-fluorophenylthiocarbamide.*—Bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) was added to the nitrophenylfluorophenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 30 minutes and kept overnight. The bromo-addition compound was collected, dried in vacuum and reduced with sulphurous acid in the usual way. On basification with ammonia (*d* 0.880) and recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, 4'-nitro-5-fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained in pale yellow crystals, m.p. 252-53°. (Found: S, 11.2. $C_{13}H_8O_2N_3FS$ requires S, 11.1 per cent).

(ii) *Synthesis from 5-fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole by way of 5-fluoro-1-chlorobenzthiazole.* (A). *5-Fluoro-1-chlorobenzthiazole.*—2 G. of 5-fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole (Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147) in 10 c.c. of hydrochloric acid were diluted with water, cooled to 0° and diazotised with sodium nitrite (1 g. in 10 c.c. of water). A further 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were then added to the mixture which was boiled and

thereafter distilled in steam. The aqueous distillate was extracted with ether and the product obtained after removal of the ether on a steam-bath was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, when 5-fluorochlorobenzthiazole was obtained in the form of soft silky needles, m.p. 97-98°, yield 0.45 g. (Found: Cl, 19.3. C_7H_5NClFS requires Cl, 19.0 per cent). (B). An intimate mixture of 5-fluoro-1-chlorobenzthiazole (0.1 g.) and *p*-fluoroaniline (0.08 g.) was heated in a test tube over a small flame until a violent reaction took place. On basification and recrystallisation from methyl alcohol—ethyl acetate, 4'-nitro-5-fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained which had m.p. 245° alone and m.p. 249-250° when mixed with the specimen obtained from *s-p*-nitrophenyl-*p*-fluorophenylthiocarbamide and bromine.

An attempt to prepare 5-fluoro-1-chlorobenzthiazole by heating *p*-fluorophenylthiocarbimide with phosphorus pentachloride in a sealed tube at 150-160° (cf. Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1879, **12**, 1126; 1880, **13**, 8; Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 458) proved unsuccessful; the bulk of the fluorophenylthiocarbimide being recovered unchanged after 7 hours heating, accompanied by what appeared to be a derivative of phenylisocyanide dichloride.

Synthesis of 4'-fluoro-5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole from 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole and p-fluoroaniline.—An intimate mixture of 1 g. of 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole (Part III, *loc. cit.*) and *p*-fluoroaniline (0.55 g.) was condensed in the usual way and the basified product was recrystallised from ethyl acetate, when it was obtained in short pale greenish yellow crystals, m.p. 278-79°. yield 0.6 g. (Found: S, 11.3. $C_{13}H_9O_2N_3FS$ requires S, 11.1 per cent). A mixture of this base with 4'-nitro-5-fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole (m.p. 252°) melted at 222°.